

FACTORS INFLUENCING UNDERGRADUATES' USAGE OF ICT FOR ACADEMIC WORK

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Introduction

Information and communication technology is used widely in the field of education due to its increasing benefits in the teaching and learning process. ICT integration in the field of education is common around the world and is implemented by both private and public sector institutions. Many studies have been conducted to investigate the relationship between usage of ICT and academic performance and have found out the positive relationship between them. For instance a study conducted on technology use and academic performance showed out that there is a direct positive relationship with technology usage and students' academic performance (Rashid & Asghar, 2016). Further, a study done on identifying teachers' acceptance of ICT usage for academic work was shown positive and they appreciated the use of ICT in teaching and learning (Theng & Hua, 2008)

Integration of ICT in education gives significant benefits for both students and lecturers in aspects like, it is easy for understanding, presents facts in a more creative and attractive way, improves efficiency and effectiveness, improves collaboration, improves engagement, knowledge retention and encourages individual learning etc. (Edmunds, Thorpe & Conole, 2012; Meerza & Beauchamp, 2017). At the same time, for the successful integration of ICT for academic activities, it is important to understand the students' perception or attitude towards usage of ICT in academic work (Meerza & Beauchamp, 2017), because if the universities or educational institutions do not have a clear idea about students' acceptance of the technology, it will be difficult to reap the maximum benefits of the technology and tools employed.

Hence this study aims to fill the gap which most literature have not touched, which is to find out the factors affecting undergraduates' attitudes on ICT usage for academic work, the extent to which students use of ICT for academic activities and finally there by to understand how the relationship between those identified factors affect on students' attitudes and usage of ICT in academic work.

Methodology

The conceptual model and hypotheses of this study was formulated mainly based on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) which is one of the popular models, which helps to model how people come to admit and utilize new technologies (Kalayou, Endehabtu & Tilahun, 2020). The model focuses on factors determining behavioral intention to use new technologies from the end user's perspective. Researcher has extended the TAM model to explore the factors that affect Intention to Use of technology in Learning Community (Edmunds, Thorpe & Conole, 2012; Liu et al., 2010). They have added factors such as subjective norm and awareness of services. Therefore, conceptual model consists of core variables of user motivation on technology usage, i.e., perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, subjective norms, awareness of services and attitudes toward technology. Of these elements, perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, awareness of services and subjective norms directly or indirectly explain the behavioral intention to use technology and thereby behavioral intention influence the actual usage.

Figure 1. Conceptual model for the study

H1: Behavioral Intention will have positive influence on actual usage of ICT.

H2: Attitude to use will have positive influence on behavioral intention.

H3: Perceived usefulness will have positive influence on behavioral intention.

H4: Perceived usefulness will have positive influence on attitude to use.

H5: Perceived ease of use will have positive influence on perceived usefulness.

H6: Perceived ease of use will have positive influence on attitude to use.

H7: Awareness of services will have positive influence on attitude to use.

H8: Subjective norms will have positive influence on behavioral intention.

A quantitative approach was used to perform the study and a google form was used to obtain responses from a sample of 114 undergraduates from a selected national university in Sri Lanka. The collected data was analyzed in form of descriptive analysis and inferential analysis and hypothesis testing was conducted using smart PLS software.

Results and discussion

Results found from this study can be discussed under the following categories.

Validity reliability and hypothesis testing

The findings of the study are backed by reliability and validity indicators found in descriptive analysis. Results in the table 1 indicate that all the values of “Cronbach’s Alpha” and “Composite reliability” are more than 0.7 and thus internal consistency reliability and indicator reliability was established (Hair et al.,2014). Simultaneously average variance extracted (AVE) values were above 0.5 and non-of the constructs cross correlations exceeds the square root of each constructs AVE. Therefore, convergent validity and discriminant validity were established respectively for the study (Hair, Ringle & Sarstedt, 2011).

Table 1. Cronbach’s Alpha values, Composite Reliability values and Average Variance Extracted values

Construct	Cronbach’s Alpha	Composite reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Actual usage (AU)	0.915	0.946	0.855
Behavioral intention (BI)	0.913	0.939	0.794
Attitude towards usage (ATU)	0.880	0.926	0.807
Perceived usefulness (PU)	0.955	0.965	0.848
Perceived ease of use (PEOU)	0.925	0.943	0.770
Subjective norms (SN)	0.877	0.923	0.799
Awareness of services (AWS)	0.843	0.897	0.687

The next step after establishing good convergent and discriminant validity was to assess the structural model to test the proposed relationships. As shown in Table 2, the results showed that undergraduates’ usage of ICT for academic work was significantly influenced by behavioral intention,

attitude towards use, perceived ease of use and awareness of services. These results provide support for H1, H2, H5, H6 and H7. Contrary to research expectations, perceived usefulness and subjective norms did not have an effect on behavioral intention. Hence, H3, H4 and H8 were not supported in this study.

Table 3: Summary of the Hypothesis testing results

Hypothesis	Relationship	P Value	Result
H1	Behavioral intention -> Actual usage	0.000	Supported
H2	Attitude towards use -> Behavioral intention	0.000	Supported
H3	Perceived Usefulness - > Behavioral intention	0.265	Not supported
H4	Perceived Usefulness - > Attitude towards use	0.466	Not supported
H5	Perceived ease of use_ ->Perceived Usefulness	0.000	Supported
H6	Perceived ease of use_ -> Attitude towards use	0.000	Supported
H7	Awareness of services -> Attitude towards use	0.001	Supported
H8	Subjective norms - > Behavioral intention	0.111	Not supported

Factors affecting undergraduates' attitudes towards usages of ICT for academic work.

Findings of the study revealed that **perceived ease of use** and **awareness of services** were found to have a significant influence on attitudes of undergraduates to use ICT for academic work which is consistent with pervious literature (Cassim & Obono, 2011; Teo et al., 2009; Teo & Beng Lee, 2010;). It was also found that perceived usefulness and subjective norms are not significantly influencing behavioral intention, which is inconsistent with some pervious literature (Salleh & Albion, 2004; Teo et al., 2009; Teo & Beng Lee, 2010;).This finding implies that undergraduates do not consider the believes and practices of people who

influence their behavior much and the perceived usefulness of ICT, when deciding to use ICT for studies. Hence, as a further research, one can explore the reasons behind this insignificant influence of perceived usefulness and while university administration can take measures to improve perceived ease of use and awareness of services or technology when formulating strategies to improve ICT adoption for studies among undergraduates.

Extent of ICT usage by undergraduates for academic activities.

Extent of ICT usage for academic work by undergraduates was found significant since the descriptive analysis resulted 47.4% of the respondents use ICT for studies several times a day and 42.1% use every day which is a significant amount in total. Further the remaining 10.5% responded to use ICT for educational purposes several times a week or less. This shows that based on the sample of data collected, the majority of undergraduates used ICT for academic work every day or even several times a day.

Conclusion

This study was formulated to find what factors might affect undergraduates' attitudes to adopt ICT for academic works and the extent to which they use ICT for academic works. None of the respondents were in poor knowledge of ICT based on descriptive analysis data and majority of them use ICT for academic works several times a day, daily or at least several times a week. Out of the taken factors (Perceived usefulness, Perceived ease of use, awareness of service and subjective norms) this study found out what factors influence significantly and what affect insignificantly and their direct and indirect relationships to attitude to use, intention to use and actual usage of ICT.

Limited sample size, the limited number of factors considered in the study and less diversity in the study area can be considered as the limitations of this research, which can be improved in further research done in relation to

attitudes of undergraduates towards ICT adoption for academic work. Practically, the university can take the above finding when formulating strategies to improve ICT adoption for studies among undergraduates.

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